

S3C

WT
clone 25
clone 25 + dox

EVI1

B-actin

3D

		EVI1 IP			
		Control		Inhibitor	
		PLASS	PLDLS	PLASS	PLDLS
		FLAG	FLAG	FLAG	FLAG
doxycycline (72hrs)		-	+	-	+

EVI1

CTBP2

		input			
		Control		Inhibitor	
		PLASS	PLDLS	PLASS	PLDLS
		FLAG	FLAG	FLAG	FLAG
doxycycline (72hrs)		-	+	-	+

EVI1

CTBP2

FLAG

S1B

